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**A MODERN APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS OF
GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS**

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Annotation

Generalized periodontitis is characterized by progressive destruction of soft and hard periodontal tissues. The principal objective of treatment is reduction or elimination of pathogenic subgingival microflora, restoration of damaged periodontal structures, and stabilization of achieved therapeutic outcomes.

Due to the unfavorable clinical course of the disease, surgical intervention remains one of the most effective treatment approaches. Contemporary therapeutic protocols should include early diagnosis, comprehensive periodontal evaluation, and rational combination of conservative, surgical, and supportive treatment modalities. Only an integrated multidisciplinary approach can ensure long-term stabilization of periodontal status and prevention of disease progression.

Keywords:

Periodontitis, periodontal surgery, diagnosis, periodontal tissues, комплексная therapy.

Introduction

Currently, a considerable number of patients with periodontal diseases seek dental care in outpatient clinical practice. Among these patients, special attention is given to individuals diagnosed with generalized periodontitis, a condition characterized by progressive inflammatory-destructive changes frequently accompanied by tooth mobility, severe gingival inflammation, secondary occlusal deformities, and esthetic as well as functional impairment.

According to investigations conducted at the Department of Periodontology of Wonkwang University School of Dentistry (Korea), the prevalence of generalized periodontitis within the examined cohort reached approximately 1.5–2.0%. Significant gender-related differences in disease occurrence were not identified. Generalized forms of periodontitis were observed substantially more frequently than localized variants, while the average patient age was approximately 35 years.

Difficulties associated with timely diagnosis and adequate treatment of generalized periodontitis contribute to progressive destruction of periodontal tissues, including alveolar bone resorption, reduction of tooth-supporting function, dentition deformation, and eventual partial or complete tooth loss. Furthermore, chronic periodontal infection may contribute to development of purulent-inflammatory processes within the maxillofacial region, creating significant risks for general health and quality of life.

Delayed diagnosis frequently reduces the effectiveness of therapeutic interventions. At the same time, the quantity and quality of scientific investigations in this field continue to expand. Among the most promising contemporary approaches are tissue engineering methods and regenerative technologies aimed at restoration of periodontal structures.

Particular importance should also be given to optimization of preoperative assessment and preparation of patients undergoing periodontal surgical treatment. In clinical practice, ineffective therapeutic outcomes are often associated with insufficient consideration of systemic conditions and disorders affecting

microcirculation, tissue oxygenation, and reparative potential. Such factors may negatively influence postoperative healing and overall prognosis.

Therefore, therapeutic measures in patients with generalized periodontitis should be directed not only toward local periodontal lesions but also toward systemic conditions and functional disturbances affecting the organism as a whole.

The above-mentioned considerations confirm the necessity for implementation of modern highly effective комплексная treatment approaches aimed at restoration of anatomical and functional characteristics of the dentofacial system and elimination of associated systemic disturbances in patients with generalized periodontitis.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study was to analyze contemporary scientific literature dedicated to periodontal diseases and modern methods of diagnosis and treatment of generalized periodontitis.

Materials and Methods

A literature review was performed using scientific medical journals indexed in international databases including eLibrary, RSCI, Higher Attestation Commission databases, and PubMed.

Results and Discussion

Generalized periodontitis develops as a consequence of interaction between multiple etiological and pathogenetic factors, including microbial invasion, genetic predisposition, immunological status, and environmental influences that determine onset, progression, and severity of the disease.

The presence of harmful habits, particularly smoking and inadequate oral hygiene, contributes significantly to destruction of the periodontal complex compared with individuals adhering to proper hygienic practices.

The disease demonstrates a wave-like clinical course characterized by alternating periods of exacerbation and remission, resulting in variable clinical manifestations during examination. During remission, patients may not report subjective complaints; gingival tissues may appear pale pink, although periodontal probing often reveals deep periodontal pockets. Despite the absence of overt inflammatory

signs, destruction of periodontal ligament structures and supporting tissues may continue.

Periods of remission may persist from several weeks to several months or even years and are interrupted by episodes of disease exacerbation. During exacerbation phases, progressive destruction of the alveolar process and periodontal ligament occurs. Clinical examination frequently reveals gingival inflammation ranging from mild to severe forms, gingival hyperplasia, and bleeding upon probing. In some cases, spontaneous purulent exudation from periodontal pockets may be observed.

Prognosis of generalized periodontitis largely depends on timely diagnosis. Early detection contributes to prevention of disease progression and reduction of severe alveolar bone loss. Genetic predisposition also plays an important role, supporting the necessity for preventive examination of close relatives of affected patients.

Conservative therapy remains the principal treatment approach during initial stages of generalized periodontitis. In cases characterized by mild or moderate periodontal destruction, treatment generally includes mechanical debridement combined with systemic or local antimicrobial therapy. Therapeutic interventions should be directed toward elimination of etiological microbial factors and correction of modifiable risk factors.

An important role in disease progression is additionally played by the individual immune response to pathogenic dental biofilm microorganisms, which is determined by genetic and systemic host-related factors.

Genetic predisposition is considered a non-modifiable risk factor for generalized periodontitis. Nevertheless, because disease progression is strongly associated with microbial biofilm accumulation and behavioral factors, effective control of dental plaque in susceptible individuals remains critically important. Even minimal plaque accumulation in predisposed patients may initiate humoral and cellular immune-inflammatory responses [2].

Systemic Antibacterial Therapy

Systemic antibiotic therapy remains an important component in treatment of generalized periodontitis because certain periodontal pathogens, including

Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans and *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, cannot always be completely eliminated by mechanical therapy alone.

Tetracycline antibiotics were previously widely used due to their ability to accumulate within periodontal tissues and suppress growth of *A. actinomycetemcomitans*. Additionally, tetracyclines inhibit collagenase activity, thereby reducing connective tissue destruction and promoting bone regeneration. However, increasing microbial resistance has necessitated use of alternative antibacterial regimens and combination therapies.

Currently, one of the most effective approaches involves combined administration of amoxicillin and metronidazole for approximately 7–8 days. Microbiological identification of periodontal pathogens and evaluation of antibiotic sensitivity are not always mandatory in routine practice because empirically selected combined regimens often demonstrate favorable clinical and economic effectiveness. Selection of systemic antibiotics should nevertheless consider patient-specific factors, including concomitant diseases, allergic reactions, and medical history [3].

Local Antimicrobial Therapy

Local antimicrobial treatment is also considered necessary in generalized periodontitis, particularly in patients presenting with deep periodontal pockets, persistent exudation, and insufficient response to mechanical debridement and systemic antibiotics.

The principal advantage of local drug delivery systems is achievement of high antimicrobial concentration directly within periodontal pockets while minimizing systemic adverse effects characteristic of systemic antibacterial therapy [4].

Scaling and Root Planing (SRP)

Scaling and Root Planing (SRP) represents a fundamental nonsurgical periodontal treatment procedure involving mechanical removal of supra- and subgingival dental deposits and smoothing of root surfaces.

The procedure may be performed using manual curettes, ultrasonic scalers, and air-abrasive systems. SRP is generally completed in one or several visits and contributes

to significant reduction of bacterial load. Following adequate SRP, root surfaces should become clean, smooth, and free from microbial biofilm and calculus deposits. However, SRP alone does not always ensure complete elimination of pathogenic microorganisms and their metabolic products from deep periodontal pockets, which explains reduced effectiveness in advanced periodontal lesions.

Full-Mouth Disinfection

Quirynen proposed an alternative antimicrobial protocol involving one-stage full-mouth disinfection. This method includes comprehensive sanitation of the oral cavity performed during a single treatment session.

The protocol involves:

- tongue disinfection with chlorhexidine;
- complete removal of dental deposits;
- oral rinsing with chlorhexidine solutions;
- irrigation of periodontal pockets with antiseptic agents.

This approach may improve clinical outcomes during early stages of periodontitis compared with isolated SRP procedures. Nevertheless, chlorhexidine use requires caution because high concentrations may provoke allergic reactions, contact dermatitis, itching, and mucosal irritation in susceptible individuals. Safety during pregnancy and lactation remains insufficiently investigated; therefore, use in these populations should be carefully limited [5].

Laser Therapy and Photodynamic Therapy

Laser therapy and photodynamic therapy (PDT) are increasingly utilized as adjunctive treatment methods aimed at suppression of pathogenic microorganisms within periodontal pockets.

Particularly effective and minimally traumatic results have been demonstrated using gas-helium-neon and semiconductor lasers based on gallium arsenide. Laser irradiation exhibits bactericidal and detoxifying properties associated with:

- improvement of local microcirculation;
- increased leukocyte migration;
- activation of proteolytic enzymes;

destruction of pathogenic microorganisms.

Laser waves are capable of penetrating deeply into inflamed periodontal tissues and exerting therapeutic effects within pathological sites [6].

Photodynamic therapy additionally produces noninvasive antimicrobial effects through formation of singlet oxygen and free radicals that destroy pathogenic microflora. PDT demonstrates high clinical effectiveness and several important advantages:

- reduced treatment time;
- rapid microbial elimination;
- absence of anesthesia requirement;
- preservation of healthy tissues;
- reduced risk of bacterial resistance formation.

At present, SRP combined with PDT and laser irradiation is considered one of the most promising minimally invasive treatment approaches for generalized periodontitis. Combined application of these modalities provides significantly superior clinical outcomes compared with isolated use of each method individually. Regular periodontal monitoring during early treatment stages allows objective evaluation of therapeutic effectiveness [7].

Analysis of scientific publications dedicated to nonsurgical treatment of generalized periodontitis demonstrates that the disease may be successfully controlled using contemporary therapeutic methods aimed at suppressing progression of pathological inflammatory destruction and stabilizing periodontal tissues.

Therapeutic interventions aimed at reducing periodontal pocket depth and preventing progressive alveolar bone destruction should begin with primary or adjunctive mechanical antimicrobial therapy combined with systemic antibiotic administration. Current recommendations suggest initiating antibacterial therapy approximately 24–48 hours before Scaling and Root Planing (SRP) or other mechanical debridement procedures and continuing the antibiotic course during the active treatment phase.

Reevaluation of periodontal status is generally performed within 4–6 weeks after completion of initial therapy. In the absence of substantial clinical improvement, clinicians may implement additional combinations of conservative methods and antimicrobial regimens. When nonsurgical therapy proves ineffective, transition to surgical treatment becomes necessary [8].

Surgical Treatment of Generalized Periodontitis

Surgical treatment of generalized periodontitis represents a complex of therapeutic interventions aimed at preventing further destruction of periodontal tissues and progressive alveolar bone loss in cases associated with delayed diagnosis or insufficient effectiveness of conservative treatment.

To minimize tissue trauma and undesirable postoperative consequences, modern laser technologies are increasingly incorporated into periodontal surgery. However, in patients with severe periodontal tissue destruction, surgical intervention may temporarily increase tooth mobility and worsen clinical stability. Therefore, individualized evaluation of risks and benefits is essential prior to treatment planning [9].

Contemporary reparative periodontal surgery is directed toward restoration of anatomical integrity and functional rehabilitation of periodontal tissues. Widespread use of autografts, xenografts, alloplastic materials, and biological modifiers such as insulin-like growth factor, A-PRF, I-PRF, and extracellular matrix proteins has significantly expanded regenerative treatment possibilities.

Periodontal Flap Surgery

For elimination of periodontal pockets, flap surgery remains one of the principal surgical approaches. Both displaced flap techniques and procedures preserving gingival papillae are commonly utilized in periodontal practice.

Combination of surgical treatment with antibacterial therapy significantly decreases microbial load and periodontal pocket depth, contributing to stabilization of periodontal tissues.

Guided Bone Regeneration and Bone Grafting

Rapidly progressing destructive changes in alveolar bone require timely therapeutic intervention. Among the most effective regenerative methods with favorable long-term outcomes are Guided Bone Regeneration (GBR) and bone grafting procedures.

The contemporary market of стоматологические biomaterials includes:

- autogenous grafts;
- allogeneic grafts;
- xenogeneic grafts;
- alloplastic synthetic substitutes.

Autogenous grafting involves transplantation of bone tissue from one anatomical site to another within the same individual and remains the gold standard due to its high osteogenic and regenerative potential confirmed by histological investigations. Additional advantages include absence of disease transmission risk and reduced immunological response.

However, disadvantages of autogenous grafting include limited donor tissue volume and possible pathological changes at the donor site.

Allografts and Xenografts

Advances in tissue engineering and biomaterial technologies have created broad possibilities for correction of periodontal bone defects. Allotransplantation involves transplantation of bone tissue between genetically different individuals. To minimize rejection risk, cellular components are removed from donor grafts during specialized processing procedures.

Clinical studies have demonstrated successful elimination of significant intrabony defects using allograft materials.

Xenografts used for reconstruction of lost periodontal tissues are commonly derived from bovine, porcine, or coral materials. Combination of xenogeneic graft materials with purified collagen or synthetic polypeptides activates regenerative processes and promotes formation of secondary periodontal ligament structures.

Collagen materials demonstrate high biocompatibility due to low allergenicity and biodegradability. These preparations reduce inflammatory activity and accelerate wound healing.

Synthetic Bone Substitutes

Synthetic graft substitutes include osteoconductive polymers, granules, cements, and osteoinductive proteins that stimulate osteogenesis, cementogenesis, and periodontal ligament formation. Osteoconductive materials function as passive matrices for newly formed bone tissue.

Among the most widely used alloplastic biomaterials are:

- hydroxyapatite;
- beta-tricalcium phosphate;
- bioactive glass.

Guided Tissue Regeneration (GTR)

Guided Tissue Regeneration (GTR) is based on application of barrier membranes that prevent epithelial migration and undesirable granulation tissue formation, thereby creating favorable conditions for regeneration of periodontal connective tissue attachment by specialized periodontal cells.

Membranes may be fabricated from biological materials or obtained from autologous platelet concentrates. Expanded polytetrafluoroethylene membranes remain among the most frequently used materials in periodontal regenerative surgery.

Numerous experimental and clinical studies have confirmed the effectiveness of membrane technologies combined with grafting materials. Modern modifications of these methods allow predictable treatment of complex three-wall and combined periodontal defects.

Biological Modifiers and Platelet Concentrates

Application of biological modifiers, including insulin-like growth factor, platelet-derived growth factor, platelet-rich plasma, and extracellular matrix proteins, positively influences both clinical and radiological outcomes.

Platelet-rich plasma contributes to regeneration of damaged periodontal tissues because platelets play a key role in wound healing through initiation of coagulation cascades, stimulation of angiogenesis, and activation of reparative cellular responses.

Platelets additionally contain fibrinogen, fibronectin, and vitronectin, which activate osteoconductive processes and function as structural matrices for regeneration of bone and connective tissues. Pronounced osteoinductive and osteoconductive properties of these biomaterials contribute to restoration of both quantity and quality of lost alveolar bone [11].

Treatment of generalized periodontitis remains a complex clinical challenge requiring an interdisciplinary approach. Delayed diagnosis significantly increases the probability of tooth loss, which in advanced stages may reach more than half of affected dentition units. Tooth loss at a young age negatively influences psychological status, social adaptation, and patient behavior.

Correction of esthetic and functional disturbances in such patients is often achievable only through combined periodontal and orthodontic therapy, prosthodontic rehabilitation, and implant-supported treatment approaches.

Long-term maintenance therapy is essential for preservation of achieved treatment outcomes and prevention of disease recurrence. Supportive periodontal care should continue throughout the patient's lifetime. Psychotherapeutic support may also exert positive influence on treatment adherence and overall rehabilitation success, particularly when initiated during the early stages of multidisciplinary management [12].

Conclusion

Generalized periodontitis is characterized by progressive destruction of soft and hard periodontal tissues. The principal therapeutic objective is reduction or elimination of pathogenic subgingival microflora, restoration of destroyed periodontal structures, and stabilization of achieved clinical outcomes.

Due to the unfavorable prognosis associated with progressive periodontal destruction, surgical treatment is considered highly effective in advanced clinical

cases. Contemporary therapeutic protocols should include early diagnosis, comprehensive periodontal evaluation, and rational combination of conservative, surgical, regenerative, and supportive treatment methods.

Only an integrated multidisciplinary approach can ensure long-term stabilization of periodontal tissues, preservation of dentition, and improvement of patient quality of life.

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